

MATHEMATICAL SKILLS AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE IN MODULAR DISTANCE LEARNING

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to determine the level of mathematical skills among pupils and their relationship with academic performance in Mathematics during modular distance learning. The study utilized a correlational research design with the aid of test questionnaires to determine the level of math skills among the respondents. A documentary method was also utilized to gather the participants' Mathematics grades. The arithmetic mean was used to evaluate the pupils' math skills, and the Spearman rho correlation coefficient measured the relationship between math skills and academic performance. Results indicated that both math skills and academic performance met minimum expectations. The correlation coefficient of 0.599, with a p-value of 0.000, demonstrated a moderate and significant relationship between the two variables. These findings suggest that mathematical skills significantly influence academic performance in Mathematics. Pupils' grades could vary based on their level of math skills, though other factors, such as the learning modality, may also play a role. The study recommends that the government provide schools with facilities to develop and sustain students' math skills, given their impact on academic performance. Future research may build on this study to explore additional variables affecting academic performance.

Keywords: *Mathematical skills, Academic performance, Modular distance learning, Correlational study, Elementary education, Spearman rho, Quantitative research*

INTRODUCTION

Mathematics is a pervasive subject essential for all age groups and circumstances. It introduces children to meaningful concepts, skills, and knowledge that are applicable in daily life and across various disciplines, thus necessitating comprehensive and in-depth learning (Attard, 2020). Early mathematical skills are foundational for more advanced capabilities, much like a sturdy foundation is crucial for a house's stability. The Partnership for 21st Century Skills (P21) identifies mathematics as a core subject, emphasizing that mathematical proficiency is crucial for both academic success and effective functioning in everyday life.

The COVID-19 pandemic has disrupted traditional face-to-face learning, prompting educational institutions to adopt Modular Distance Learning (MDL) as a critical response to ensure continuity in education. Despite this adaptation, students often struggle with mathematics, a trend observed even before the pandemic (Grade Power Learning, 2018). Many factors, including the learning modality and students' mathematical skills, impact their performance. This study investigates the relationship between Grade Six pupils' mathematical skills and their academic performance in mathematics during MDL. It aims to identify the challenges students face and propose effective strategies, tools, or interventions to enhance their mathematical performance in this instructional mode.

Literature Background

Today's mathematics education demands a diverse, complex, and integrated set of knowledge and skills. In the Philippine K-12 curriculum, mathematics is designed to be meaningful and relevant, catering to students' ability levels and societal needs (DepEd, 2012). Lyons and Ansari (2015) demonstrated that mathematical skills are critical predictors of academic success. The hierarchical nature of mathematical skill acquisition means that foundational skills are crucial for developing advanced competencies (Advanced et al., 2008; Luculano, 2018).

The Philippine mathematics education program focuses on essential skills and contents organized into Numbers and Number Sense, Measurement, Geometry, Patterns and Algebra, and Statistics and Probability (SEI-DOST & MATHTED, 2011). Studies emphasize that mathematical ability significantly influences students' academic performance (Farooq et al., 2011; Narad & Abdullah, 2016). However, the Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS) revealed persistent issues in students' mathematics achievement globally and locally (Maltese & Tai, 2011).

During the pandemic, the Department of Education (DepEd) implemented distance learning modalities, with MDL emerging as the preferred method due to its accessibility (Bernardo, 2020). Modular instruction has been shown to foster independent learning and improve performance in mathematics (Paspasan, 2015; Mahmud, 2012). The study's theoretical framework includes the Mutualism Theory, Constructivism, and Self-Directed Learning Theory, emphasizing the interconnected development of cognitive skills,

knowledge construction, and independent learning (Van der Maas et al., 2006; Cruickshank, 2006; Garrison, 1997).

The researchers of this study aim to delve deeper into the relationship between students' Mathematical skills and their academic performance in Mathematics in the context of Modular Distance Learning. The researchers believe that this study will make significant contribution to the body of knowledge in this area and provide valuable insights for educators, policy-makers, and other stakeholders in the field of education, enhancing mathematics education amidst the ongoing challenges posed by the pandemic.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the level of Mathematical skills of the Grade Six pupils and its relationship with their Academic Performance in Mathematics during Modular Distance Learning at Daus Central Elementary School for the School Year 2021-2022.

Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the pupils' level of mathematical skills in terms of the following:
 - 1.1. numbers and number sense;
 - 1.2. geometry;
 - 1.3. patterns and algebra;
 - 1.4. measurement; and
 - 1.5. statistics and probability?
2. What are the pupils' academic performance in Mathematics during modular distance learning?
3. Is there a significant relationship between pupils' Mathematical skills and their academic performance during modular distance learning?

METHODOLOGY

The researchers employed a non-experimental research specifically the correlational design to determine the relationship between pupils' mathematical skills and their academic performance during Modular Distance Learning. Moreover, the research study was quantitative in nature, involving a test questionnaire. A documentary method was utilized to gather the academic performance in Mathematics of the research participants.

This study was conducted in Daus Central Elementary School during the Academic Year 2021-2022. It is a public elementary school with a total number of sixteen teachers, five

non-teaching personnel, and administrative staff. The participants of the study were the Grade Six pupils who are officially enrolled at Dauis Central Elementary School for the School Year 2021-2022, which consists of two sections with an exact population of 60 students. A simple random sampling was used wherein 80% of the total population were the actual respondents, while the remaining 20% were the respondents for the pilot testing.

The researchers formulated a test questionnaire with a total of 25 items in the evaluation of the pupils' mathematical skills. The test questionnaires were divided into 5 categories, namely Numbers and Number Sense, Measurement, Geometry, Patterns and Algebra, and Statistics and Probability with 5 items per skill.

The test questionnaires were based from two sources. First, in crafting the Table of Specification (TOS), the learning competencies were derived from the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) by DepEd, which was also used by the Grade Six Math teachers in Dauis Central Elementary School. Second, the questions were based on the official Mathematics Framework for Philippine Basic Education by the Science Education Institute, Department of Science and Technology (SEI-DOST), and the Philippine Council of Mathematics Teacher Education (MATHTED) and were tailored to fit the current study. A pilot testing, followed by item analysis were conducted to determine the validity and reliability of the test questionnaires.

The data gathered were treated through the following statistical procedures. To determine the pupils' level of mathematical skills from the test questionnaires, the researchers computed the arithmetic mean with the formula:

$$\bar{X} = \frac{\sum x}{n}$$

Where:

\bar{X} = arithmetic mean

$\sum x$ = sum of all scores

n = number of respondents

In interpreting the scores obtained from the test questionnaires, the following score description was used.

SCORE	DESCRIPTION	INTERPRETATION
5	Excellent	The student demonstrates an excellent level of mathematical skills' application and understanding of the learning competencies and is able to use these skills with a high degree of effectiveness.
4	Very Good	The student demonstrates a very good level of mathematical skills' application and understanding of the learning competencies and is able to use

		these skills with a considerable degree of effectiveness.
3	Good	The student demonstrates a good level of mathematical skills' application and understanding of the learning competencies and is able to use these skills with a moderate degree of effectiveness.
2	Fair	The student demonstrates a fair level of mathematical skills' application and understanding of the learning competencies and is able to use these skills with a limited degree of effectiveness.
0-1	Poor	The student demonstrates a poor level of mathematical skills' application and understanding of the learning competencies and is able to use these skills with a little or no degree of effectiveness.

With regards to student's academic performance in Mathematics subject, the researchers used the following grading scale with its corresponding descriptors based on DepEd Order No. 8, s. 2015.

GRADING SCALE	DESCRIPTION	INTERPRETATION
90-100	Outstanding	Students' performance exceeds expectations. Displays at all times a high level of performance-related skills.
85-89	Very Satisfactory	Students' performance often meets expectations, exhibits a very satisfactory performance in Mathematics.
80-84	Satisfactory	Indicates a satisfactory performance and meets basic/minimum expectations.
75-79	Fairly Satisfactory	Students' performance rarely meets expectations and/or one or more of the learning competencies were not met.
Below 75	Did Not Meet Expectations	Students' performance consistently falls below expectations. Significant improvement is needed.

To determine the relationship between the pupils' mathematical skills and academic performance, the Spearman rho was used with the formula:

$$\rho = 1 - \frac{6 \sum d_i^2}{n(n^2 - 1)}$$

Where:

ρ = Spearman's rank correlation coefficient

d_i = difference between the two ranks of each observation

n = number of observations

To determine the interpretation of the correlation, the proceeding range was used:

Absolute value of r	Interpretation
± 0.00-0.20	Negligible Correlation
± 0.21-0.40	Low Correlation
± 0.41-0.60	Substantial Correlation
± 0.61-0.80	High Correlation
± 0.81-1.00	Very High Correlation

RESULTS

Table 1
Pupils' Level of Mathematical Skills
N=48

Score Range	Description	Numbers and Number Sense		Geometry		Patterns and Algebra		Measurement		Statistics and Probability	
		F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
5	Excellent	13	27%	18	38%	4	8%	0	0%	1	2%
4	Very Good	18	38%	17	35%	16	33%	14	29%	11	23%
3	Good	8	17%	8	17%	15	31%	18	38%	19	40%
2	Fair	5	10%	4	8%	11	23%	9	19%	8	17%
0-1	Poor	4	8%	1	2%	2	4%	7	15%	9	19%
Average		3.6 (Good)		4 (Very Good)		3.1 (Good)		2.8 (Fair)		2.7 (Fair)	
GENERAL MEAN		3.3 (Good)									

Table 2
Pupils' Academic Performance in Mathematics during
Modular Distance Learning
N=48

Grading Scale	Description	Frequency	Percentage	Ranking
90-100	Outstanding	10	21%	3
85-89	Very Satisfactory	12	25%	2
80-84	Satisfactory	21	44%	1
75-79	Fairly Satisfactory	5	10%	4
Below 75	Did Not Meet Expectations	0	0%	5
AVERAGE		84.4 (SATISFACTORY)		

Table 3
Relationship Between Pupils' Mathematical Skills and Academic Performance in
Mathematics during Modular
Distance Learning
N=48

Relationship	Correlation Coefficient (Spearman Rho)	Description	P-Value	Decision
Mathematical Skills and Academic Performance in Mathematics during Modular Distance Learning	0.599	Substantial Correlation	0.000	Significant; Reject Null Hypothesis

DISCUSSION

Table 1 presents the Pupils' Level of Mathematical Skills such as Numbers and Number Sense, Geometry, Patterns and Algebra, Measurement and Statistics and Probability with their corresponding frequency and percentage distribution values.

In terms of Numbers and Number Sense, out of 48 respondents, there are eighteen pupils (18) or 38% got a "Very good" rating with a score range of 4. Meanwhile, only four pupils which is equivalent to 8% got a "Poor" rating with a score range of 0-1 on the test questionnaire. The rest (i.e., 26 or 54%) of the population have varying results although there is a close difference between them. This means that most of the pupils are doing good in Mathematics in terms of numbers and number sense in modular distance learning since more than half of the respondents got a score range of 3-5 and based on the table presented above, its average is 3.6 which categorized as "Good." According to Cunningham (2020), more students have stronger number sense than others who demonstrate an understanding of concepts and show mastery of the operations of whole numbers, decimals, fractions, ratio and proportion, percent, and integers. Yet, several students with poor number sense struggle with basic math operations like addition and multiplication.

When it comes to their level of skills in Geometry, 38% of the class who got an "Excellent" rating and only one pupil which is an equivalent to 2% in the class got "Poor" rating. The overall Geometry skills of the total respondents is 4 which described as "Very Good." Hence, this is indeed a good baseline considering that lower number of students have fair to poor level of Geometric skills while there are more students who have excellent to very good level of on this skill. Such students have develop better understanding of shapes and figures because they are able to study and analyze their properties (SEI-DOST and MATHTED, 2011).

As to the pupils' level of skills in Patterns and Algebra, there are sixteen pupils or 33% got the rating of "Very good," whereas, two pupils who constitutes the 4% of the class got only a poor rating in the test. Whilst only a few students (specifically 8%) got an excellent score, majority got good to fair scores from the test. Patterns and Algebra got an average score of 3.1 which described as "Good." It can be noticed that there are slight changes in the pattern of scores from the previous skills mentioned above. Furthermore, this relates to the study of Yenilmez and Avcu (2009) which suggested that 6th graders have the habit to perform operations without thinking on the algebraic situations. Therefore, some students have difficulties in comprehending the abstract structure of Algebra.

In terms of Measurement, it depicts that the highest rank belongs to the score range of 3 having a percentage of 38% with a "Good" rating which comprises 18 respondents. However, the score range of 5 was the lowest rank having no student among the class got an "Excellent" rating from the test. Pupils' measurement skills got an average score of 2.8 which described as "Fair." This manifests that it's remarkably harder for most students to master this skill but there are still pupils who are trying to demonstrate their

ability to extend their basic knowledge on concepts pertaining to applications involving speed, distance, time, and measuring the surface area of solid/space figures (SEI-DOST and MATHTED, 2011).

With regards to Statistics and Probability, the table shows that there are 19 pupils or 40% got the rating of “Good,” which is almost half of the total respondents. On the contrary, only one pupil which is an equivalent to 2% of the total number of pupils in the class got an “Excellent” rating. Pupils’ skills in Statistics and Probability got an average score of 2.7 which described as “Fair.” This conforms that mastery in this skill is harder than mastering the others since there is a close gap between the frequency of scores ranging across 0-4 and acquiring an excellent score of 5 is a struggle among most of the students.

In general, table 1 also shows the average score of each Mathematical skills of the total respondents. By looking at the table, a comparison between the skills can be observed and analyzed. Among the five skills, it reveals that the students performed very well in Geometry, since it got the highest average score of 4 described as “Very good” which suggests that its easier for students to visualize, analyze, and identify various geometric figures, thus, raising the level of understanding of geometric concepts.

On the other hand, Statistics and Probability ranks the lowest with an average score of 2.7 which can be identified as “Fair” level, and it clearly means that they’re struggling to develop appropriate skills for collecting, organizing, analyzing data, estimating, and using probabilities for making predictions of events (SEI-DOST and MATHTED, 2011). According to Cunningham (2020), statistics is especially tough for kids who struggle with fractions and percentages and with comparing values. Nonetheless, it can be observed that the general mean of the overall Mathematical skills of the grade six pupils is 3.3 which is described as “Good.” This implies that the students demonstrate a good level of mathematical skills' application and understanding of the learning competencies and is able to use these skills with a moderate degree of effectiveness.

Moreover, this relates to the study of Gallo and Johnson (2008) wherein they pointed out that a substantial number of students lack the mastery of very elementary math concepts. Hence, they suggested that professors should identify students with weak basic math skills early on so that some type of remediation can be done to bring these students up to par. This is in consonance with Advanced Math Success (2008) that a solid knowledge of basic arithmetic skills is the foundation on which more complicated math is built. According to Silva et al. (2006), mastery of prerequisite skills spells success and ease with which the students can hurdle the mathematical theories and computations.

The result also supports Mutualism Theory by Van der Maas et al. (2006) where development is seen as a complex system of (positively) interacting processes, where learning one process (skill) supports learning of the other processes in the system. Hence, growth in a particular math skill positively influences that of other math skills (i.e., Geometry and Numbers and Number Sense). In contrast, pupils with low mathematical skills have deficit to some of the skills as shown from the result of the student’s average scores in Measurement and Statistics and Probability. It is also likely that children differ

in the degree to which different skills influence each other's growth and should be examined by future researchers.

Table 2 shows the frequency and percentage distribution values of the pupils' academic performance in Mathematics during modular distance learning.

As shown in the table, it depicts that almost half of the respondents (44%) were considered as "Satisfactory" with a grading scale of 80-84 which got the highest frequency rank. Meanwhile, at the bottom-ranked, 10% of the respondents which marked as "Fairly satisfactory" with a grading scale of 75-79, and luckily, none of the respondents got a grade below 75 which categorized as "Did not meet expectations".

It is in this table wherein we can conclude that the overall math performance of students during modular distance learning is 84.4 which is categorized as "Satisfactory." This implies that each student had met the minimum expectations. However, only five students (10%) received the "Fairly satisfactory" grade. According to Paulos (as cited in Stites, 2012), people think that math is only for a selected few or the left-brained ones. However, Paulos disagreed with this as everyone has the ability to do Mathematics and problem solving as long as they know the basics.

The Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study 2019 (TIMSS) showed that the Philippines scored 'significantly lower' than any other country that participated in grade 4 math and science assessments. Problems related to Mathematics achievement are still evident not only in the Philippine setting but also right in other countries. Inevitably, students with fairly satisfactory grades may also be attributed to the learning modality used by the learners which is the modular distance learning and should also be taken into consideration. Some students probably don't prefer learning through modules which results to lower math skills and lower academic performance in Mathematics. According to Saragih and Habeahan, (2014), many students see Mathematics as a difficult subject to understand. This happens because Mathematics is presented in a form that is less attractive and looks difficult for students to learn.

In addition, Piaget's cognitive development theory supported that student learning is dependent on the teaching method that the teacher implements inside the classroom. The knowledge they acquire is affected by the teacher's way of presenting facts and figures. This challenges curriculum planners to do something about the new normal education.

Table 3 displays the relationship between the pupils' mathematical skills and academic performance in Mathematics during modular distance learning. As reflected in the table, results revealed that the correlation coefficient of the computed two variables is 0.599 which implies a substantial correlation and the p-value of .000 denotes a significant relationship, thus null hypothesis is rejected. The result claims that the mathematical skills of the students have a moderate effect on their academic performance, hence, there is still a significant relationship between variables.

This supports the related study of Nizoloman (2013) which highlights an important result that provides further information concerning the links between student mathematical skill and achievement in Mathematics. The results of the study showed that mathematical skill is a strong predictor on students' achievement in Mathematics. In the same manner, the results substantiate the studies of Tremblay, et al. (2000) who were studying the impact of the sample variables, supported the hypothesis that mathematical ability contributes to the prediction of achievement in statistics as suggested by Harlow, et al. (2002).

In addition, an educational study of 35,000 preschoolers conducted by Duncan (2013) revealed that the importance of early math skills is paramount. Also, Siegler and Pyke (2013) pointed out that elementary Mathematics skills and students' knowledge of fractions and divisions predict their achievement in Mathematics during high school.

However, looking back at the overall result of the pupils' math skills which is 3.3 described as "Good" and their academic performance is 84.4 which is described as "Satisfactory." It can be observed that both results meet the minimum expectation. That is to say, the higher the mathematical skill of a student is, the higher his/her performance in Mathematics and the lower the mathematical skill of a student is, the lower his/her performance in Mathematics. Here, their math skills are on average level, so is their math academic performance.

Nevertheless, those who weren't able to perform well in the test questionnaire possibly lack the necessary skills needed. Thus, they demonstrate a fair-poor level of mathematical skills' application and understanding of the learning competencies and are able to use these skills with a limited or little degree of effectiveness which also results to lower grades in math. This implies that Grade 6 pupils have a long way to go before an outstanding performance in Mathematics could be achieved. This is supported by the Discussion Paper on the Enhanced K+12 Basic Education Curriculum (2010) stating that in the National Achievement Test (NAT) for Grade 6 in SY 2009-2010, the passing rate is only 69.21 percent.

The studies carried out by Nail (2013) seemed to lend credence to the efficacy of mathematical ability groupings on learning outcomes. Despite the students demonstrating confidence in their abilities, the overall performance on the Mathematics achievement test was quite poor. The average score was about 50% and almost half the students achieved this or lower. This is also in corroboration with WAEC, (2003) whose findings have also shown that poor performance of students in Mathematics could be traced to their mathematical ability.

This significant relationship between math skills and academic performance may also be attributed to the learning modality used by the learners which is the modular distance learning. The Self-Directed Learning Theory of Donn Randy Garrison (1997) as cited by Szalay (2020) supported this result. According to this theory, individuals take the initiative to acquire the necessary skills they must acquire in moving from face-to-face formats to distance learning, with or without the assistance of others. Therefore, modular distance learning is also important to consider with regards to pupils' math skills and academic

performance which also means that learning modality could as well as be a factor that affects both variables in the study.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the overall result of the pupils' Math skills is "Good," and their average academic performance is considered "Satisfactory" which denotes a moderate correlation. Therefore, there is a significant relationship between pupils' mathematical skills and their academic performance in Mathematics during modular distance learning. The result implies that the application of Math skills proved potent as one of the factors that influenced pupils' academic performance in Math. The learners could have high or low grades depending on the level of their Math skills, although some factors may still influence their performance such as the learning modality.

Recommendations

After a thorough examination of the findings and conclusion of the study, the researchers offer the following recommendations:

1. The government may provide schools with facilities that will develop and sustain students' Math skills as it affects students' performance in Mathematics.
2. The administration of Daus Central Elementary School may capacitate teachers by giving them training, seminars and workshop with regards to teaching Mathematics subject effectively and to improve Mathematics instruction in this mode of learning.
3. Mathematics teachers may determine their students' skills towards Mathematics before starting the course to enable them to select and employ the appropriate teaching strategy in a modular distance learning.
4. Teachers may also use innovative teaching aids other than modules (concrete objects), integrate ICT, and interactive game-based instruction focusing on improving pupils' math skills, as well as evaluate and monitor their progress on each skill especially to pupils with low mathematical skills.
5. The future researchers may anchor their further studies related to the effect of math skills on the academic performance of students in other learning areas in Mathematics to confirm the effectiveness of the use of math skills.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study was conducted with strict adherence to ethical standards to ensure the integrity and ethical soundness of the research process. Informed consent was obtained from all respondents, ensuring that they were fully aware of the study's objectives, procedures, and their rights as participants. Respondents were informed of their freedom to withdraw from the study at any time without any repercussions. Anonymity of the respondents was

strictly maintained, and all personal identifiers were removed from the data to protect their privacy.

The well-being of the respondents was safeguarded throughout the study. Measures were taken to ensure that no harm came to any participant as a result of their involvement in the research. There was no conflict of interest in the conduct of this study, and all procedures were carried out impartially. Plagiarism was strictly avoided by ensuring all sources were properly cited, and original work was maintained. Furthermore, there was no bias in the interpretation of the findings; data were analyzed objectively to reflect the true outcomes of the research. The results of this study were used purely for academic and research purposes to contribute to the body of knowledge in the field of education

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